

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D7.10 (update)

Seabird distribution and vulnerability to wind farms

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) conducted during pre-construction phase of offshore wind farms clearly identified interactions between turbines and marine wildlife, especially seabirds, as a concern requiring further investigation. Displacement and mortality associated with collision could lead to negative impacts on seabird populations, and needs to be assessed on a case-by-case basis irrespective of turbine design.

In this study, we collected data on flight behaviour, sensitivity to disturbance and conservation status for 81 seabird species present in European waters before calculating Collision and Displacement Vulnerability Indices to assess the most at risk species to wind turbines. We combined those indices with distributions of 12 commonly occurring seabird species in the North-East Atlantic based on surveys conducted between 1980 and 2018, to generate vulnerability maps for breeding, wintering and migration periods when risk is likely to vary.

We shown that auks, loons and ducks are highly vulnerable to displacement while some procellariiforms and larids are vulnerable to collision with wind turbines. Vulnerability to collision and displacement at the seabird community level are not evenly distributed, and vary with season according to the distribution of the most at risk species. Vulnerability maps identified areas of higher vulnerability at the European scale, highlighting where further surveys, monitoring, tracking studies, or mitigation might be needed.

Finally, we identified numerous species for which there are high uncertainties due to lack of data. Within X-ROTOR, methods to reducing these uncertainties will be explored, taking into account the unique design of the X-ROTOR turbine.

Note: This document is an update of the original deliverable

List of acronyms

BACI	Before-After-Control-Impact
CRM	Collision Risk Models
CVI	Collision Vulnerability Index
DVI	Displacement Vulnerability Index
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
GPS	Global Positioning System
SDM	Species Distribution Model

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Following the increasingly concerning IPCC climate predictions (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2021) and in order to reach the Paris Agreement Objectives (UNFCCC, 2015), global greenhouse gas emissions must be reduced. Renewable energy has a fundamental part to play in global decarbonisation, and in 2018, targets of the European Union Renewable Energy Directive were revised upward, aiming for at least a 32% share of renewable energy (European Parliament, 2018). In response, many countries are turning to wind energy, with short term EU targets driving expansion of onshore/offshore wind farms.

To ensure the lowest environmental cost per kW produced, effects of wind farms on ecosystems need to be carefully assessed (May et al., 2017). Environmental Impact Assessments (EIA) conducted during pre-construction clearly identified interactions between turbines and marine wildlife, especially seabirds, as a concern (Bergström et al., 2014). Seabirds are among the most threatened of all bird groups globally (Dias et al., 2019), with effects of offshore wind farms including habitat loss due to barrier effect (Masden et al., 2010), displacement (Welcker and Nehls, 2016) and mortality by collision (Desholm, 2006), leading to population declines (Searle et al., 2014). Assessment of collision and displacement risks is often a requirement of consenting, and its over or underestimation could have profound effects on the sustainability of populations.

1.2 Seabird vulnerability to offshore wind farms

Assessing seabird vulnerability to marine energy infrastructures relies on 1) the understanding of the drivers of their at-sea distribution to deduce potential overlaps with marine anthropogenic activities, 2) the description of their at-sea behaviour in response to the marine infrastructures (flight height, attraction and avoidance for example) to assess collision and disturbance risks, 3) the evaluation of those risk impacts on local and global populations (through measurements of fitness and/or adult survival) according to species conservation status.

1.2.1 At-sea seabird distribution and behaviour

Assessing seabird vulnerability to marine energy infrastructures relies on 1) the understanding of the drivers of their at-sea distribution to deduce potential overlaps with marine anthropogenic activities, 2) the description of their at-sea behaviour in response to the marine infrastructures (flight height, attraction and avoidance for example) to assess collision and disturbance risks, 3) the evaluation of those risk impacts on local and global populations (through measurements of fitness and/or adult survival) according to species conservation status.

1.2.2 At-sea seabird distribution and behaviour

Seabirds spend an important part of their time at sea (Schreiber and Burger, 2002) and are often unreachable during most of their life-cycle, strongly limiting data acquisition on their at-sea distribution and behaviour. Although several approaches including boat/plane surveys, tracking devices and modelling techniques exist to determine seabird at-sea distribution, all have underlying assumptions, strengths and weaknesses. For example, surveys enable identification of seabirds at the species level and calculation of density over large areas (especially when made by plane (see, Rogan *et al.*, 2018 for example)) providing a snapshot of local

population abundance and distribution. Further, boat surveys can provide crucial observations of seabird behaviour (such as flight height and macro/meso/micro avoidance) in wind turbine context, allowing robust collision risk calculation. However, survey data only gives a snapshot of individual seabird locations without taking into account important but fluctuating parameters such as weather conditions or prey abundance that shape seabird at-sea distribution. Finally, due to logistical constraints, surveys covering whole basin areas occur infrequently, generally at a decadal basis (Waggitt *et al.*, 2020), while those focusing on short periods cover limited areas.

Complementary to at-sea surveys, many seabirds species have been equipped (Bernard *et al.*, 2021) with a range of loggers such as GPS, providing highly accurate location and movement data, while accelerometer and TDR (Temperature Depth Recorder) provide additional behavioural data (Bennison *et al.*, 2018). Battery size and overall weight of the devices constrain recording duration, making it difficult to obtain accurate location data for smaller species year-round. Further, as loggers usually need to be recovered to download stored data, equipped individuals are generally breeding individuals which come back regularly to the colony. Therefore, tracking studies usually do not take into account juveniles and non-breeders, omitting an important part of the population that could distribute and behave differently than breeding individuals (Votier *et al.*, 2017). Further, many studies are based on small sample sizes and on particular colonies, making it difficult to extrapolate across larger spatio-temporal scales, and are rarely conducted in wind farm context (but see Thaxter *et al.*, 2019).

Distribution modelling is increasingly being used to understand and predict the at-sea distribution of seabirds. Some approaches use correlative models (e.g. Species Distribution Models) linking mathematically, species occurrence with environmental covariates experienced at those locations (Elith and Leathwick, 2009). These can be used to project and predict species distribution across space and time. However, such models usually rely on extensive covariate data and struggle to include all biologically relevant processes driving species distribution while remaining simple enough for analysis using existing computer processing power. Mechanistic models linking organismal functional traits to environmental features are becoming more frequently used to describe animal distributions, but vary in terms of complexity. One of the simplest is the foraging radius model approach (Soanes *et al.*, 2016; Critchley *et al.*, 2020). Model calculation only requires location and size of colonies for the species considered, and estimates of the species' mean maximum foraging range. It then provide a species density estimation around each colony, assuming that seabird density decrease with the distance to the breeding site. Such calculation is possible at large spatial scales as long as colony locations are known, but is limited to the breeding season and only considers adult breeding birds. In addition, it does not take into account particular foraging strategies, such as alternating short and long foraging trips (Shoji *et al.*, 2015) or following fishing vessels for discard consumption (Darby *et al.*, 2021), leading to discrepancies between model outputs and observed distributions.

1.2.3 *Assessing seabird vulnerability to collision and disturbance*

Before-After-Control-Impact (BACI) studies may be conducted as part of wind farm developments with dedicated surveys (Petersen *et al.*, 2006) throughout the year, allowing identification of species using the area pre, during, and post construction to determine attraction/avoidance to the site and infrastructure. Collision could be monitored at existing wind farms using radar (Cook *et al.*, 2018), cameras (Matzner, Warfel and Hull, 2020) or direct observations. Further, numerous collision risk models have been developed and

integrated to EIA, such as the Band model, predicting the probability of a bird to collide with a turbine blade (Band, 2012). Such models usually rely on seabird distribution and flight characteristics observed at existing sites (height and speed especially) as well as information on wind farm features (number of and spacing between turbines, blade pitch and speed, height of the rotor swept area in particular). However, such calculations are not always feasible at the early developmental stage of wind farm projects when turbine characteristics are not yet defined and siting of installations within licensing areas remains to be decided. Vulnerability indices (Garthe and Hüppop, 2004; Certain *et al.*, 2015; Critchley and Jessopp, 2019) represent an alternative approach to assess species most at-risk to collision and displacement, and can be combined with seabird distribution data in spatial risk assessment useful for identifying areas suitable for offshore development while minimising potential impacts on biodiversity. Vulnerability indices combine multiple factors (see methods) to generate an overall vulnerability score for individual species which includes a conservation component based on the sensitivity of a population to impacts.

Due to the large spatial scope of the X-ROTOR project and the preliminary nature of the turbine design, the calculation of broad Collision and Displacement Vulnerability Indices is particularly useful. This allows for the identification of areas where further studies on collision risk, including avoidance due to the speed and acoustic signature of the turbine may be appropriate.

1.3 Deliverable details

This report forms part of the Socio-environmental Impact work package of the X-ROTOR project, building robust Collision and Displacement Vulnerability Indices and providing a framework to include them in spatial risk assessments at the European scale. For 81 seabird species either breeding or migrating through European waters, this report aims to:

- 1) Review species-specific vulnerability factors.
- 2) Identify the degree of uncertainty linked to vulnerability factors.
- 3) Calculate Collision and Displacement Vulnerability Indices, and identify the most at-risk species.
- 4) Apply the vulnerability scores to modelled species distribution at a European scale.
- 5) Combine species vulnerability maps to generate a single map of seabird vulnerability at the community level.

2 Methods

We included 81 seabird species present in European waters throughout the year according to BirdLife International (<http://datazone.birdlife.org/species/search>), and calculated for each of them, vulnerability scores to collision and displacement induced by wind turbines.

2.1 Collision and Displacement Vulnerability Indices calculations

Collision and Displacement Vulnerability indices combine multiple factors that are grouped into three main components : 1) the habitat overlap factors, which determine the extent to which a seabird may use wind farm areas according to its avoidance or attraction to the site, 2) the collision risk factors, that quantify the likelihood of a species to collide with turbines, 3) the conservation factors, which are combined to give a

score of population level sensitivity to mortality caused by collision. Combining those three components gives a vulnerability score to wind turbines at the population level.

2.1.1 *Habitat overlap factors*

Factors have been taken from various sources (Furness, Wade and Masden, 2013; Wade *et al.*, 2016; Kelsey *et al.*, 2018; Critchley and Jessopp, 2019; Fliessbach *et al.*, 2019) or extrapolated from closely-related species when unavailable. Factors were scored on a five-point scale from very low (0.2) to very high vulnerability (1). These factors take into account how a seabird species could be attracted/disturbed by wind turbines structures (A1) as well as by vessels/helicopters present in the areas during the construction or maintenance phases (A2) and how it could impact species according to its degree of habitat use flexibility (A3). Indeed, species having weak habitat specialisations are likely to be less greatly affected by any level of disturbance.

2.1.2 *Collision risk factors*

Collision risk is determined by the percentage of flight that is spent at the height of turbine blades (B1), the percentage of time in flight (B2), the species flight agility (B3) and its nocturnality (B4). We previously conducted an extensive review of those factors for the 81 species of interest (see D7.9 deliverable) that we completed with the work conducted by Wilmott and colleagues (2013). Based on advice within the project consortium, we considered the rotor swept area of the X-ROTOR turbines to be between 20m-150m above sea level. We scored the percentage of flight spent in the rotor sweep area according to Certain *et al.*, 2015 between very low (0.2) to very high vulnerability (1). Other collision risk factors were scored following Furness *et al.*, 2013. As some species display different flight behaviour during migration (flying higher and at night for example), we scored each factors inside and outside migration period. When observations weren't available regarding specific migration flight behaviour, factors were considered as the same as the rest of the year.

2.1.3 *Conservation factors*

Conservation factors were taken from Furness *et al.*, 2013 but were updated to be geographically relevant for the European extent of the X-ROTOR project. Conservation status were considered globally (C1) and at the European scale (C2) from the IUCN Red-List (<https://www.iucnredlist.org> and BirdLife International, 2015). We scored them from Least Concern (0.2) to Critically Endangered (1). Percentage of biogeographic population (C3) was calculated as the European population percentage of the global population for each species according to the IUCN and scored according to Furness *et al.*, 2012. Adult survival rate (C4) were mostly taken from review made by Willmott, Forcey and Kent, 2013 and Critchley and Jessopp, 2019, and completed by species specific studies (see Appendix 1). This last factor was scored according to Fliessbach *et al.*, 2019.

Factor sources and details about scoring are presented in Table 1. All factors were scored from very low (0.2) to very high vulnerability (1) and in order to put them on the same scale, values were divided by 5 when factors have been previously scored from 1 to 5 (see Furness *et al.*, 2013 for example).

2.1.4 *Vulnerability indices calculations*

We combined vulnerability factors using the equations (see below) developed by Certain *et al.*, 2015, considering primary and aggravating factors which mediate the influence of primary factors through a weighting (see Certain *et al.*, 2015 for further details on weighting and its corresponding sensitivity analysis).

The Collision Vulnerability Index (CVI) was calculated as follows:

$$CVI = ((1 - A1 \pm uA1 \times A1) \times (B1 \pm uB1 \times B1) \times B2) \left(1 - \frac{\frac{(B3+B4)}{2}}{\frac{(B3+B4)}{2} + 0.5}\right) \times \left(\frac{C1 + C2 + C3}{3}\right)^{1 - \frac{C4}{(C4+0.5)}}$$

As disturbance could reduce collision risk by reducing the number of seabirds in the wind farm area, the collision risk index was lowered by including disturbance when combining habitat overlap (A) and collision risk (B) factors. The collision vulnerability score obtained was then multiplied by the conservation score calculated combining conservation factors (C) together to finally conclude on the overall population level sensitivity to wind farms.

The Displacement Vulnerability Index (DVI) was calculated separately according to the following equation to take into account any negative effects of disturbance:

$$DVI = \left(\frac{(A1 \pm uA1 \times A1) + (A2 \pm uA2 \times A2)}{2}\right)^{\left(1 - \frac{A3}{(A3+0.5)}\right)} \times \left(\frac{C1 + C2 + C3}{3}\right)^{\left(1 - \frac{C4}{(C4+0.5)}\right)}$$

Wade and colleagues (2016) identified the percentage of time spent at the turbine blade height (B1) as well as the disturbance by structures (A1) and vessels/helicopters (A2) as the main drivers of seabird vulnerability to wind farms. As the quantity, quality and relevance of the data contributing to those factors could dramatically impact our conclusions, we reviewed or calculated the uncertainty linked with those factors. We followed the method developed by Wade and colleagues (2016) to calculate for each species an Uncertainty Level from very low (0.1) to very high (0.5) for the percentage of time spent at turbine blades height (see deliverable D7.9). For the disturbance factors (A1) and (A2), we took uncertainty levels described in Wade et al., 2016; Kelsey et al., 2018; Fliessbach et al., 2019 and Willmott, Forcey and Kent, 2013. Where the uncertainty was 25%, we rounded up to 0.3. When no data were found about uncertainty level of those factors, we considered 0.5 as the default value. Uncertainty was then included in the previous equations as $uA1$, $uA2$ and $uB1$ to obtain lower and upper confidence levels of collision and displacement vulnerability for each species.

2.1.5 Vulnerability maps

To take into account spatial variation of seabird distribution across the year in European waters, we used the best available seabird monthly distribution data provided by Waggitt and colleagues (2020) for the North-East Atlantic basin. In this important collaborative study, the authors created monthly 10km resolution density maps for 12 seabird species (Atlantic puffin, common guillemot, razorbill, black-legged kittiwake, herring gull, lesser black-backed gull, Manx shearwater, northern fulmar, European shag, northern gannet, great skua and European storm petrel) after collating and standardizing survey observations conducted over 2.68 million km between 1980 and 2018 and modelling data to overcome issues with patchy and uneven coverage.

As seabirds are usually migrants, we averaged the distribution maps during the breeding season (June to August), the autumn (September to October) and spring (April to May) migration periods as well as during the overwintering months (November to March) to obtain four maps identifying the different area used through the year for each species.

Collision vulnerability maps were then produced for each period of the year by dividing seabird density in each 10km² grid square by 1- vulnerability score. Collision vulnerability scores were first normalised between 0.99 and 0 to give greater distinction between high and low risk species. Maps were produced for each species and then summed together to assess overall risk to all seabirds in the region. This method was repeated using the DVI scores to produce separate maps of displacement vulnerability.

Table 1. Vulnerability factors included in Collision and Displacement Vulnerability Indices calculations

Vulnerability factors	Sources	Scoring
Habitat overlap factors		
Disturbance by wind turbines structures (A1)	Furness, Wade and Masden, 2013; Wade <i>et al.</i> , 2016; Kelsey <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Critchley and Jessopp, 2019; Fliessbach <i>et al.</i> , 2019 or extrapolated from closely-related species when unavailable. Sources for each species are given in Appendix 1.	From very low (0.2) to very high vulnerability (1). Values were divided by 5 when factors have been previously scored from 1 to 5.
Disturbance by vessels/helicopters (A2)		From very low (0.2) to very high vulnerability (1). Values were divided by 5 when factors have been previously scored. When taken from Fliessbach <i>et al.</i> , 2019; we converted it as follows: 1-5=0.2; 5.1-10=0.4; 10.1-15:0.6; 15.1-20=0.8; 20.1-25=1
Habitat use flexibility (A3).		From very low (0.2) to very high vulnerability (1). Values were divided by 5 when factors have been previously scored from 1 to 5.
Uncertainty level related to A1 and A2 ($\alpha A1$, $\alpha A2$)	Wade <i>et al.</i> , 2016; Kelsey <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Fliessbach <i>et al.</i> , 2019 and Willmott, Forcey and Kent, 2013. Sources for each species are given in Appendix 1.	From very low (0.1) to very high (0.5). When no data were found we considered 0.5 as the default value.
Collision risk factors		
Percentage of flight spent at the height of turbine blades (B1)	Extensive review of those factors (see D7.9) completed with Willmott and colleagues' work (2013).	Scoring follows Certain <i>et al.</i> , 2015: 0-5%: 0.2; 6-10%: 0.4; 11-15%: 0.6; 16-20%: 0.8; 20-100%: 1
Percentage of time in flight (B2)		Scoring follows Furness <i>et al.</i> , 2013 after dividing scores by 5: 0-20%: 0.2; 21-40%: 0.4; 41-60%: 0.6; 61-80%: 0.8; 81-100%: 0.9
Flight agility (B3)		From very high (0.2) to very low agility (1).
Species nocturnality (B4)		From very low (0.2) to very high nocturnality (1).
Uncertainty level related to B1 ($\alpha B1$)		Calculated following Wade <i>et al.</i> , 2016 (results in D7.9 deliverable).
Conservation factors		
Global IUCN status (C1)	IUCN red list (https://www.iucnredlist.org)	Least Concern: 0.2; Near Threatened: 0.4; Vulnerable: 0.6; Endangered: 0.8; Critically Endangered: 1
European IUCN status (C2)	BirdLife International 2015	
Percentage of the biogeographical population (C3)	Calculated from IUCN data (https://www.iucnredlist.org)	Scoring follows Furness <i>et al.</i> , 2012: <1%: 0.2; 1-4%: 0.4; 5-9%: 0.6; 10-19%: 0.8; \geq 20%: 1
Adult survival rate (C4)	Sources for each species are given in Appendix 1.	Scoring follows Fliessbach <i>et al.</i> , 2019 after dividing scores by 5: <0.75: 0.2; >0.75: 0.4; >0.8: 0.6; >0.85: 0.8; >0.9: 1

3 Deliverable outcomes

Vulnerability factor values and corresponding uncertainty levels are presented in Table 2 while Collision and Displacement Vulnerability Index scores with ranking are shown in Table 3. The most vulnerable species to collision are those that spent significant time flying at turbine blade height and/or are nocturnal and/or are assumed to be less sensitive to wind turbine structures. Great cormorant, greater scaup, some procellariiforms such as northern fulmars and manx shearwaters, as well as some petrels and few gulls and terns species are mostly concerned. In contrast, loons, ducks, some shearwaters and auks have strong disturbance/avoidance behaviours, making them less vulnerable to collision but highly vulnerable to displacement (see Figure 1). Some auks and terns are expected to migrate at night, increasing largely their vulnerability to collision during those periods.

Figure 1. Relationship between Collision Vulnerability Index (CVI) and Displacement Vulnerability Index (DVI) scores for all species. Colour coding relates to taxonomic family group.

Table 2. Vulnerability factor values and corresponding uncertainty levels. When a factor displays two values for a species, the first one correspond to the value outside migration periods, while the second is the value taken during this part of the year.

Species	B1	zB1	B2	B3	B4	A1	zA1	A2	zA2	A3	C1	C2	C3	C4
Arctic Jaeger	0.4	0.3	1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.8	1
Arctic Loon	0.2	0.4	0.6	1	0.2/1	1	0.3	0.8	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.8	0.6
Arctic Tern	0.2	0.3	1	0.2	0.2/1	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.2	1	0.6
Atlantic Puffin	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.6	0.2/1	0.6	0.3	0.6	0.1	0.6	0.6	0.8	1	1
Audouin's Gull	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.2	1	1
Audubon's Shearwater	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.6	1	1	0.5	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.8	1
Balearic Shearwater	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.6	1	1	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.2	1	1	1	0.4
Band-rumped Storm petrel	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.2	1	1	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.6	1
Barrow goldeneye	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.6	1	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.2
Black Guillemot	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.6	0.4	1	0.1	0.8	0.2	0.2	1	0.8
Black Tern	0.2	0.5	1	0.2	0.2/1	1	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.8	0.6
Black-headed Gull	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	1	0.6
Black-legged Kittiwake	0.6	0.1	0.2/0.6	0.2	0.6	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.6	0.6	1	0.8
Black-necked Grebe	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.8	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.2

Species	B1	zB1	B2	B3	B4	A1	zA1	A2	zA2	A3	C1	C2	C3	C4
Bulwer's Petrel	0.2	0.5	1	0.6	1	1	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.4	1
Caspian Gull	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.2	NA	0.6
Caspian Tern	0.2	0.5	1	0.2	0.2/1	1	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.8
Common Eider	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.8	0.6	1	0.3	0.6	0.3	0.8	0.4	0.6	1	0.8
Common Goldeneye	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.2	1	0.4
Common Gull-billed Tern	0.2	0.5	1	0.2	0.2/1	1	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.8	0.8
Common Loon	0.2	0.5	0.4	1	0.2	1	0.4	0.8	0.5	0.6	0.2	0.6	0.2	0.8
Common Murre	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.8	0.4/1	0.8	0.1	0.6	0.1	0.6	0.2	0.4	0.8	1
Common Scoter	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.1	1	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.2	1	0.4
Common Tern	0.4	0.2	1	0.2	0.2/1	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.2	1	0.8
Cory's shearwater	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.6	1	1	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	1	1
Desertas Petrel	0.2	0.5	1	0.6	1	1	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.6	0.6	1	0.2
European Herring Gull	0.8	0.2	0.8	0.4	0.6	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.4	1	0.6
European Shag	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.8	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.2	1	0.8
European Storm-petrel	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.2	1	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	1	0.6
Glaucous Gull	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.8	1

Species	B1	zB1	B2	B3	B4	A1	zA1	A2	zA2	A3	C1	C2	C3	C4
Goosander	1	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.4	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.2
Great Black-backed Gull	1	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.6	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	1	1
Great Cormorant	0.8	0.3	0.8	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.2	1	0.8
Great Crested Grebe	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.2	0.4/1	0.6	0.4	0.6	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Great Shearwater	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.6	1	1	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	1
Great Skua	0.2	0.3	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	1	0.8
Greater Scaup	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.8	1	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.6	0.6	0.6
Harlequin Duck	0.2	0.5	0.2	NA	0.2	1	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.8
Horned Grebe	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.8	0.4	1	0.3	0.6	0.4	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.4	0.2
Iceland Gull	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.2	0.6/1	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	1	1
Ivory gull	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.2	1	0.8
King eider	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.4	1	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.6	1
Leach's Storm-petrel	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.2	1	0.8
Lesser Black-backed Gull	0.8	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	1	0.8
Lesser Crested Tern	0.2	0.5	1	0.2	0.2/1	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.8
Little Auk	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.4	1	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.2	1	0.6

Species	B1	zB1	B2	B3	B4	A1	zA1	A2	zA2	A3	C1	C2	C3	C4
Little Gull	0.8	0.2	0.6	0.2	0.4/1	0.8	0.5	0.2	0.1	0.6	0.2	0.4	1	0.6
Little Tern	0.6	0.5	0.8	0.2	0.2/1	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.8	0.2	0.2	1	0.6
Long-tailed Duck	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.6	1	0.4	0.6	0.1	0.8	0.6	0.6	1	0.2
Long tailed Jaeger	0.2	0.5	1	0.2	0.4/1	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.8	0.8
Manx Shearwater	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.6	1	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	1	0.8
Mediterranean Gull	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.2/1	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.2	1	0.6
Mew Gull	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.6/1	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	1	0.6
Monteiro's Storm petrel	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.2	1	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.6	0.6	1	1
Northern Fulmar	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.8	1	1
Northern Gannet	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.6	0.2	0.8	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	1	1
Pallas'gull	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.4/1	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.6
Pomarine Jaeger	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.2	0.6/1	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.8	0.6
Razorbill	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.8	0.4	0.8	0.1	0.8	0.1	0.6	0.4	0.4	1	0.8
Red Phalarope	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Red-billed tropicbird	0.2	0.5	0.8	0.6	0.2	0.6	0.5	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	1
Red-breasted Merganser	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.8	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.4	1	0.4

Species	B1	zB1	B2	B3	B4	A1	zA1	A2	zA2	A3	C1	C2	C3	C4
Red-necked Grebe	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.2/1	1	0.3	0.6	0.1	0.6	0.2	0.2	1	0.2
Red-necked Phalarope	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	1	0.2
Red-throated Loon	0.4/1	0.2	0.4	1	0.2/1	1	0.2	1	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.2	1	0.6
Roseate Tern	0.2	0.5	1	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.8
Ross's Gull	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.4/1	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.6
Sabine's Gull	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.4/1	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.6
Sandwich Tern	0.4	0.2	1	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.2	0.2	1	0.8
Scopoli's shearwater	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.6	1	1	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.2	1	1
Slender-billed Gull	0.8	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.2/1	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.2	1	0.6
Sooty Shearwater	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.6	1	1	0.5	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.2	1
Steller's eider	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.4	1	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.8	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.6
Thick-billed Murre	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.4	1	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.8	1
Velvet Scoter	0.2/1	0.5	0.4	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.5	1	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.6	1	0.4
White-faced storm petrel	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.2	1	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.8	0.4	0.8
Wilson's Storm-petrel	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.2	1	1	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.8
Yelkouan shearwater	0.2	0.5	0.8	0.6	0.6	1	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.6	0.2	1	0.8

Species	B1	zB1	B2	B3	B4	A1	zA1	A2	zA2	A3	C1	C2	C3	C4
Yellow billed loon	0.2	0.5	0.4	1	0.4	1	0.4	0.8	0.5	0.8	0.4	0.6	0.2	1
Yellow legged gull	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.4/1	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.2	0.2	1	1
Zino's Petrel	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.2	1	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.8	1	0.6

Table 3. Collision and Displacement Vulnerability Index scores with corresponding ranking

Species	CVI Lower	CVI	CVI Upper	DVI Lower	DVI	DVI Upper	CVI Lower Migration	CVI Migration	CVI Upper Migration	Rank CVI	Rank DVI	Rank CVI Migration
Arctic Jaeger	0.23	0.33	0.43	0.21	0.3	0.38	0.23	0.33	0.43	4	68	7
Arctic Loon	NA	0	0.17	0.54	0.63	0.71	-0.18	0	0.24	55	14	55
Arctic Tern	0.1	0.16	0.21	0.34	0.41	0.47	0.21	0.27	0.33	29	53	17
Atlantic Puffin	0.05	0.09	0.13	0.66	0.74	0.8	0.13	0.19	0.24	42	3	33
Audouin's Gull	0.06	0.23	0.43	0.39	0.57	0.72	0.06	0.23	0.43	18	21	27
Audubon's Shearwater	NA	0	0.31	0.34	0.54	0.71	NA	0	0.31	56	29	56
Balearic Shearwater	NA	0	0.34	0.42	0.69	0.93	NA	0	0.34	57	8	57
Band-rumped Storm petrel	NA	0	0.18	0.37	0.48	0.58	NA	0	0.18	58	41	58
Barrow goldeneye	NA	0.08	0.14	0.27	0.36	0.42	NA	0.08	0.14	48	60	49
Black Guillemot	0.04	0.09	0.15	0.62	0.68	0.74	0.04	0.09	0.15	43	9	46
Black Tern	NA	0	0.17	0.4	0.52	0.62	NA	0	0.28	59	37	59
Black-headed Gull	0.1	0.14	0.17	0.29	0.36	0.43	0.1	0.14	0.17	33	61	36
Black-legged Kittiwake	0.19	0.21	0.22	0.4	0.45	0.5	0.34	0.38	0.41	21	45	5
Black-necked Grebe	NA	0.03	0.07	0.26	0.34	0.4	NA	0.03	0.07	54	64	54

Species	CVI Lower	CVI	CVI Upper	DVI Lower	DVI	DVI Upper	CVI Lower Migration	CVI Migration	CVI Upper Migration	Rank CVI	Rank DVI	Rank CVI Migration
Bulwer's Petrel	NA	0	0.31	0.27	0.45	0.6	NA	0	0.31	60	46	60
Caspian Gull	0.03	0.11	0.2	0.19	0.27	0.34	0.03	0.11	0.2	38	74	43
Caspian Tern	NA	0	0.17	0.43	0.56	0.66	NA	0	0.28	61	23	61
Common Eider	NA	0	0.15	0.68	0.79	0.87	NA	0	0.15	62	2	62
Common Goldeneye	NA	0.14	0.27	0.48	0.6	0.69	NA	0.14	0.27	34	17	37
Common Gull-billed Tern	NA	0	0.18	0.42	0.58	0.71	NA	0	0.3	63	18	63
Common Loon	NA	0	0.16	0.48	0.62	0.74	NA	0	0.16	64	16	64
Common Murre	0.06	0.09	0.11	0.63	0.66	0.69	0.11	0.14	0.17	44	11	38
Common Scoter	0.07	0.1	0.13	0.59	0.63	0.66	0.07	0.1	0.13	40	15	45
Common Tern	0.21	0.27	0.34	0.37	0.43	0.48	0.33	0.39	0.45	12	49	4
Cory's shearwater	NA	0	0.31	0.36	0.54	0.7	NA	0	0.31	65	30	65
Desertas Petrel	NA	0	0.39	0.34	0.56	0.74	NA	0	0.39	66	24	66
European Herring Gull	0.4	0.47	0.53	0.28	0.32	0.36	0.4	0.47	0.53	2	65	2
European Shag	0.11	0.16	0.21	0.44	0.54	0.63	0.11	0.16	0.21	30	31	34

Species	CVI Lower	CVI	CVI Upper	DVI Lower	DVI	DVI Upper	CVI Lower Migration	CVI Migration	CVI Upper Migration	Rank CVI	Rank DVI	Rank CVI Migration
European Storm-petrel	0.17	0.24	0.31	0.15	0.22	0.29	0.17	0.24	0.31	17	81	25
Glaucous Gull	NA	0.16	0.37	0.34	0.51	0.66	NA	0.16	0.37	31	39	35
Goosander	NA	0.11	0.21	0.3	0.39	0.47	NA	0.11	0.21	39	58	44
Great Black-backed Gull	0.33	0.38	0.43	0.36	0.4	0.43	0.33	0.38	0.43	3	56	6
Great Cormorant	0.44	0.53	0.62	0.37	0.43	0.49	0.44	0.53	0.62	1	50	1
Great Crested Grebe	0.02	0.05	0.08	0.21	0.26	0.3	0.04	0.08	0.12	51	76	50
Great Shearwater	NA	0	0.23	0.27	0.41	0.53	NA	0	0.23	67	54	67
Great Skua	0.15	0.21	0.26	0.23	0.31	0.37	0.15	0.21	0.26	22	67	31
Greater Scaup	NA	0.26	0.45	0.52	0.65	0.75	NA	0.26	0.45	14	12	20
Harlequin Duck	NA	0	0.03	0.45	0.55	0.63	NA	0	0.03	68	26	68
Horned Grebe	NA	0	0.24	0.45	0.53	0.6	NA	0	0.24	69	34	69
Iceland Gull	NA	0.18	0.41	0.43	0.58	0.71	NA	0.23	0.46	24	19	28
Ivory gull	0.06	0.22	0.4	0.36	0.53	0.67	0.06	0.22	0.4	19	35	30
King eider	NA	0	0.14	0.51	0.64	0.73	NA	0	0.14	70	13	70

Species	CVI Lower	CVI	CVI Upper	DVI Lower	DVI	DVI Upper	CVI Lower Migration	CVI Migration	CVI Upper Migration	Rank CVI	Rank DVI	Rank CVI Migration
Leach's Storm-petrel	0.17	0.25	0.33	0.17	0.26	0.34	0.17	0.25	0.33	16	77	24
Lesser Black-backed Gull	0.27	0.3	0.33	0.28	0.32	0.35	0.27	0.3	0.33	7	66	12
Lesser Crested Tern	NA	0.05	0.16	0.31	0.43	0.51	NA	0.12	0.25	52	51	42
Little Auk	NA	0	0.07	0.51	0.58	0.64	NA	0	0.07	71	20	71
Little Gull	NA	0.17	0.39	0.43	0.55	0.64	NA	0.26	0.46	27	27	21
Little Tern	0.15	0.29	0.44	0.41	0.5	0.57	0.26	0.4	0.52	9	40	3
Long-tailed Duck	NA	0	0.2	0.65	0.74	0.81	NA	0	0.2	72	4	72
Long tailed Jaeger	0.14	0.22	0.3	0.24	0.29	0.33	0.22	0.31	0.38	20	71	10
Manx Shearwater	0.24	0.3	0.36	0.15	0.24	0.31	0.24	0.3	0.36	8	78	13
Mediterranean Gull	0.04	0.16	0.32	0.33	0.48	0.6	0.11	0.28	0.43	32	42	15
Mew Gull	0.23	0.28	0.34	0.3	0.36	0.41	0.28	0.33	0.38	10	62	8
Monteiro's Storm petrel	0.21	0.31	0.39	0.17	0.29	0.38	0.21	0.31	0.39	6	72	11
Northern Fulmar	0.24	0.28	0.31	0.19	0.28	0.35	0.24	0.28	0.31	11	73	16
Northern Gannet	0.06	0.08	0.1	0.46	0.54	0.61	0.06	0.08	0.1	49	32	51

Species	CVI Lower	CVI	CVI Upper	DVI Lower	DVI	DVI Upper	CVI Lower Migration	CVI Migration	CVI Upper Migration	Rank CVI	Rank DVI	Rank CVI Migration
Pallas'gull	0.05	0.17	0.31	0.28	0.41	0.52	0.09	0.24	0.37	28	55	26
Pomarine Jaeger	0.12	0.18	0.23	0.24	0.27	0.3	0.16	0.23	0.28	25	75	29
Razorbill	0.06	0.09	0.12	0.71	0.74	0.78	0.06	0.09	0.12	45	5	47
Red Phalarope	NA	0.05	0.1	0.17	0.24	0.29	NA	0.05	0.1	53	79	53
Red-billed tropicbird	0.04	0.13	0.22	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.04	0.13	0.22	35	69	40
Red-breasted Merganser	NA	0.06	0.13	0.37	0.55	0.7	NA	0.06	0.13	50	28	52
Red-necked Grebe	NA	0	0.08	0.47	0.52	0.57	NA	0	0.14	73	38	73
Red-necked Phalarope	NA	0.09	0.19	0.32	0.44	0.53	NA	0.09	0.19	46	48	48
Red-throated Loon	NA	0	0.16	0.62	0.71	0.78	-0.28	0	0.32	74	6	74
Roseate Tern	0.06	0.13	0.21	0.31	0.4	0.46	0.06	0.13	0.21	36	57	41
Ross's Gull	0.05	0.18	0.33	0.31	0.45	0.56	0.1	0.26	0.4	26	47	22
Sabine's Gull	NA	0.09	0.22	0.26	0.36	0.44	NA	0.14	0.27	47	63	39
Sandwich Tern	0.21	0.27	0.34	0.37	0.43	0.48	0.21	0.27	0.34	13	52	18
Scopoli's shearwater	NA	0	0.31	0.33	0.54	0.72	NA	0	0.31	75	33	75

Species	CVI Lower	CVI	CVI Upper	DVI Lower	DVI	DVI Upper	CVI Lower Migration	CVI Migration	CVI Upper Migration	Rank CVI	Rank DVI	Rank CVI Migration
Slender-billed Gull	0.02	0.1	0.2	0.33	0.48	0.6	0.08	0.2	0.31	41	43	32
Sooty Shearwater	NA	0	0.69	0.26	0.56	0.88	NA	0	0.69	76	44	76
Steller's eider	NA	0	0.19	0.58	0.65	0.69	NA	0	0.19	77	25	77
Thick-billed Murre	NA	0	0.28	0.75	0.92	1.05	NA	0	0.28	78	10	78
Velvet Scoter	NA	0.18	0.31	0.65	0.78	0.88	NA	0.32	0.56	37	1	19
White-faced storm petrel	0.28	0.38	0.46	0.06	0.14	0.22	0.28	0.38	0.46	15	80	23
Wilson's Storm-petrel	NA	0	0.27	0.29	0.44	0.59	NA	0	0.27	79	59	79
Yelkouan shearwater	NA	0	0.43	0.23	0.52	0.82	NA	0	0.43	80	22	80
Yellow billed loon	NA	0	0.47	0.9	0.98	1.04	NA	0	0.47	81	7	81
Yellow legged gull	0.03	0.17	0.39	0.4	0.63	0.83	0.22	0.47	0.67	23	36	14
Zino's Petrel	0.3	0.4	0.49	0.07	0.15	0.24	0.3	0.4	0.49	5	70	9

Vulnerability maps for the 12 seabird species considered in Waggitt *et al.*, 2020 across the breeding season (see Figure 2), autumn migration (see Figure 3), winter period (see Figure 4) and spring migration (see Figure 5) show how the spatial distribution of the vulnerability to collision and displacement varies during the year. During the breeding and overwintering period, the vulnerability distribution to collision is mainly shaped by the procellariiforms (Manx shearwater and northern fulmar) distribution while the vulnerability to displacement is mainly driven by the auks (Atlantic puffin, common guillemot and razorbill) locations.

BREEDING SEASON

CVI

DVI

AUKS (Atlantic puffin, Razorbil, Common guillemot)

LARIDS (Black-legged kittiwake, Herring gull, Lesser black-backed gull)

PROCELLARIFORMS (Manx shearwater, Northern fulmar)

European shag

Northern gannet

Great Skua

European storm-petrel

Figure 2. Collision (left) and Displacement Vulnerability (right) maps during the breeding season for the 12 species considered in Waggitt et al., 2020.

AUTUMN MIGRATION

CVI

DVI

AUKS (Atlantic puffin, Razorbil, Common guillemot)

LARIDS (Black-legged kittiwake, Herring gull, Lesser black-backed gull)

PROCELLARIFORMS (Manx shearwater, Northern fulmar)

European shag

Northern gannet

Great skua

European storm-petrel

Figure 3. Collision (left) and Displacement Vulnerability (right) maps during autumn migration for the 12 species considered in Waggitt et al., 2020.

WINTER

CVI

DVI

AUKS (Atlantic puffin, Razorbil, Common guillemot)

LARIDS (Black-legged kittiwake, Herring gull, Lesser black-backed gull)

PROCELLARIFORMS (Manx shearwater, Northern fulmar)

European shag

Northern gannet

Figure 4. Collision (left) and Displacement Vulnerability (right) maps during winter for the 12 species considered in Waggitt et al., 2020.

SPRING MIGRATION

CVI

DVI

AUKS (Atlantic puffin, Razorbil, Common guillemot)

LARIDS (Black-legged kittiwake, Herring gull, Lesser black-backed gull)

PROCELLARIFORMS (Manx shearwater, Northern fulmar)

European shag

Northern gannet

Great Skua

European storm-petrel

Figure 5. Collision (left) and Displacement Vulnerability (right) maps during the spring migration for the 12 species considered in Waggitt et al., 2020.

During winter, high collision vulnerability extends into the North Sea and off West Ireland (see Figure 6) and is particularly high in the Saint George’s Chanel (between Wales and South-East Ireland). In this season, high displacement vulnerability is distributed along Irish, English, Scottish and Norwegian coasts (see Figure 6). In summer, high collision and displacement vulnerability areas are less extended than during winter and more localised near important colonies of those species. Collision vulnerability is therefore particularly important off South-West Ireland, in the West Scottish Sea near Small Isles and at the extreme North-West of Wales, whereas displacement vulnerability is high along the North coasts of Scotland, Shetland Islands, and in the Dublin and Edinburgh bays (see Figure 6).

BREEDING SEASON

All species CVI

All species DVI

WINTER SEASON

All species CVI

All species DVI

Figure 6. Total Collision (left) and Displacement Vulnerability (right) maps during breeding and winter.

During migrations, as the Collision Vulnerability Index of auks increases due to nocturnal flight behaviour, Collision and Displacement Vulnerability Indices are similarly distributed according to the distribution of those species. During autumn migration, collision vulnerability is quite similar to displacement vulnerability during winter, while during the spring migration collision vulnerability mirrors displacement vulnerability during the breeding period (see Figure 7).

AUTUMN MIGRATION

All species CVI

All species DVI

SPRING MIGRATION

All species CVI

All species DVI

Figure 7. Total Collision (left) and Displacement Vulnerability (right) maps during autumn and spring migrations.

4 Conclusions and perspectives

This analysis is an essential step in identifying the most vulnerable species to collision and displacement induced by wind turbines developments and determining areas of increased vulnerability at European scales. As demonstrated by Critchley and Jessopp, 2019, combining use of vulnerability index and distribution maps provide a powerful tool for defining the species and areas most at risk. However, due to the spatial and temporal scope of our study, we were only able to provide such maps for 12 seabird species. Waggitt and colleagues (2020) provided a framework for obtaining monthly species distributions at large scale from sparse surveys, and we hope to be able to complement this with further survey efforts.

Vulnerability maps illustrate how collision and displacement risk vary with time according to species ecology. Identifying vulnerable species and pinpointing what risk factors drive this vulnerability will allow effective mitigation to be applied. For example, turning off turbines during period of nocturnal migrations could be a solution to avoid collision with nocturnal migrants such as auks and terns while avoiding areas with high level of species endemism will diminish the mortality impacts of turbines on populations.

Tracking studies will likely be an important tool to provide crucial behavioural information and reduce uncertainties in flight height estimates and responses to turbine infrastructure for numerous species (see deliverable D7.9).

Before-After-Control-Impact studies are crucial to resolving uncertainties associated with offshore developments, particularly when assessing innovative or novel turbine designs such as the X-ROTOR concept. For example, the tip speed of the first rotors are proposed to be slower than traditional turbine designs, and with an associated decrease low frequency noise emitted by the turbine, may diminish perception of collision risk. In the opposite, second rotors are expected to emit higher level of high frequency noise, may enabling fine-scale avoidance behaviour to avoid collision. However, the broader horizontal swept area and increased number of moving turbine blades may represent increased collision risk, and should be the focus of further study. Within the X-ROTOR project, three seabird species (Atlantic puffin, Manx shearwater and Northern gannet) with high vulnerability to displacement and/or collision were tracked during the 2021 breeding season using GPS and acoustic recorders. Data will be used to better describe flight height and understand how they use acoustic cues at sea and whether frequencies emitted by the X-ROTOR design might be perceived and change birds' behaviour. These data will be further analysed within the socio-environmental impacts work package.

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Appendix 1

Details of data sources for vulnerability factors A1, A2, A3 and C4 and the uncertainty level $uA1$ and $uA2$. Sources of others factors are presented in Table 1 and Deliverable D7.9.

Species	A1	A2	A3	C4	$uA1$	$uA2$
Arctic Jaeger	Based on related species	Furness et al., 2013		Horswill & Robinson, 2015	Wade et al., 2016	
Arctic Loon	Based on related species	Furness et al., 2013		Horswill & Robinson, 2015	Wade et al., 2016	
Arctic Tern		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Atlantic Puffin		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Audouin's Gull	Based on related species			Oro et al., 1999	0.5 by default	
Audubon's Shearwater				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Balearic Shearwater	Based on related species			Arroyo et al., 2016; Oro et al., 2004	0.5 by default	
Band-rumped Storm petrel				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Barrow goldeneye	Based on related species			Wilmott et al., 2013	0.5 by default	
Black Guillemot		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Black Tern				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Black-headed Gull		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Black-legged Kittiwake		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Black-necked Grebe	Based on related species			Abt & Konter, 2009	0.5 by default	

Species	A1	A2	A3	C4	zA1	zA2
Bulwer's Petrel	Based on related species			Mougin, 1996	0.5 by default	
Caspian Gull	Based on related species			0.5 by default		
Caspian Tern	Wilmott et al., 2013					
Common Eider	Wilmott et al., 2013	Furness et al., 2013		Fliessbach et al., 2019	Wade et al., 2016	
Common Goldeneye	Wilmott et al., 2013	Furness et al., 2013		Wilmott et al., 2013	Wade et al., 2016	
Common Gull-billed Tern	Wilmott et al., 2013					
Common Loon	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016		
Common Murre	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016		
Common Scoter	Based on related species	Furness et al., 2013		Horswill & Robinson, 2015	Wade et al., 2016	
Common Tern	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016		
Cory's shearwater	Wilmott et al., 2013					
Desertas Petrel	Based on related species			Ramos et al., 2016	0.5 by default	
European Herring Gull	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016		
European Shag	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016		
European Storm-petrel	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Oro et al., 2005; Sanz-Aguilar et al., 2009	Wade et al., 2016	

Species	A1	A2	A3	C4	zA1	zA2
Glaucous Gull				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Goosander				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Great Black-backed Gull		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Great Cormorant		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Great Crested Grebe		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Great Shearwater				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Great Skua		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Greater Scaup		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Harlequin Duck				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Horned Grebe	Wilmott et al., 2013	Furness et al., 2013		Fliessbach et al., 2019	Wilmott et al., 2013	Wade et al., 2016
Iceland Gull				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Ivory gull	Based on related species			Gilchrist et al., 2008	0.5 by default	
King eider				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Leach's Storm-petrel	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wilmott et al., 2013	Wade et al., 2016	
Lesser Black-backed Gull		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Wade et al., 2016	
Lesser Crested Tern		Based on related species			0.5 by default	

Species	A1	A2	A3	C4	zA1	zA2
Little Auk	Wilmott et al., 2013	Furness et al., 2013		Wilmott et al., 2013		Wade et al., 2016
Little Gull				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Little Tern	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019			Horswill & Robinson, 2015		Wade et al., 2016
Long-tailed Duck	Wilmott et al., 2013	Furness et al., 2013		Fliessbach et al., 2019	Wade et al., 2016	Wilmott et al., 2013
Long tailed Jaeger				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Manx Shearwater		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019				Wade et al., 2016
Mediterranean Gull	Based on related species			Marvelde et al., 2009		0.5 by default
Mew Gull		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019				Wade et al., 2016
Monteiro's Storm petrel	Based on related species			Robert et al., 2015		0.5 by default
Northern Fulmar		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019				Wade et al., 2016
Northern Gannet		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019				Wade et al., 2016
Pallas'gull		Based on related species				0.5 by default
Pomarine Jaeger				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Razorbill		Critchley & Jessopp, 2019				Wade et al., 2016
Red Phalarope				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Red-billed tropicbird				Wilmott et al., 2013		
Red-breasted Merganser	Wilmott et al., 2013			Fliessbach et al., 2019		Wilmott et al., 2013

Species	A1	A2	A3	C4	zA1	zA2
Red-necked Grebe	Wilmott et al., 2013			Fließbach et al., 2019	Wilmott et al., 2013	
Red-necked Phalarope	Wilmott et al., 2013					
Red-throated Loon	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019				Wade et al., 2016	
Roseate Tern	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019				Wade et al., 2016	
Ross's Gull	Based on related species				0.5 by default	
Sabine's Gull	Wilmott et al., 2013					
Sandwich Tern	Critchley & Jessopp, 2019				Wade et al., 2016	
Scopoli's shearwater	Based on related species			Ristow, 2020	0.5 by default	
Slender-billed Gull	Based on related species			Doxa et al., 2013	0.5 by default	
Sooty Shearwater	Wilmott et al., 2013	Furness et al., 2013		Wilmott et al., 2013	Wade et al., 2016	
Steller's eider	Based on related species			Flint et al., 2000	0.5 by default	
Thick-billed Murre	Wilmott et al., 2013					
Velvet Scoter	Based on related species	Furness et al., 2013		Fließbach et al., 2019	Wade et al., 2016	
White-faced storm petrel	Based on related species				0.5 by default	
Wilson's Storm-petrel	Wilmott et al., 2013					

Species	A1	A2	A3	C4	zA1	zA2
Yelkouan shearwater	Based on related species			Oppel <i>et al.</i> , 2011	0.5 by default	
Yellow billed loon	Kelsey <i>et al.</i> , 2018	Based on related species		Kelsey <i>et al.</i> , 2018	0.5 by default	
Yellow legged gull	Based on related species			Skórka, Wójcik and Martyka, 2005	0.5 by default	
Zino's Petrel	Based on related species			0.6	0.5 by default	